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Metrology support for enhanced energy efficiency in DC transportation systems

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Abstract

This paper describes a new EU-co-funded project on metrology support for enhanced energy efficiency in DC transportation systems (e-TRENY). The project involves 5 national metrology institutes, 3 universities, 1 metro operator, and 1 consulting group. Research focuses on the following topics: i) new calibration facilities for DC transducers (up to 3 kV, 1 kA) under dynamic conditions, ii) accurate on-site losses of the converter group (power transformer – AC/DC bidirectional converter, DC/DC converter) operating in DC substations, iii) energy saving performance of transportation systems with non-conventional DC substations.

1 Introduction

The DC railway and metro systems supplied by unidirectional substations exhibit a notable energy inefficiency, primarily stemming from their incapacity to fully reclaim the energy generated during electric braking. Bidirectional substations and/or storage systems are expected to significantly improve energy efficiency, but IEC TC9, CENELEC SC9XC, and CENELEC TC14 raised concerns about the lack in this field of standard procedures for the determination of the actual performance of specific devices e.g. current measuring equipment, power transformers or converters and of efficiency of the overall system. In response to these concerns, the presented project [1] aims to tackle these issues by developing new methodologies for determining the electrical energy efficiency in DC transport systems.

2 Needs

In railway/metro/tram systems supplied by unidirectional DC substations, the energy regenerated by the traction units must be consumed within the DC railway traction grid. Any extra energy generated by electric braking is dissipated by the braking rheostat and thus wasted. Based on the energy analysis conducted using experimental data from the EMPIR project 16ENG04 MyRailS [2], [3] —data recorded during the monitoring of various railway traction units in commercial service— it was determined that a significant portion, ranging from a few percent to 50%, of the available regenerative energy is dissipated and consequently lost [4]. To address this issue of energy waste, new supply configurations that allow the flow of excess power from DC to AC (reversible substations) or/and that adopt stationary storage systems, have been proposed and are currently being installed. However, there is a strong need for a standardized methodology for the assessment of the energy efficiency performance of these new installations. In particular, methods that safeguard the designer, the supplier, the installer, and the railway infrastructure manager. The "line receptivity" is used to measure a power supply system's capacity to accept braking energy, yet there is currently no standardized definition or methodology for its measurement. Although this parameter is widely employed by electrified transportation stakeholders and is included in tender specifications, its evaluation is currently reliant on numerical simulations due to the challenges of experimental assessment. Urgently needed in the industry is the standardization of models and simulation methodologies, coupled with experimental validation, to enhance confidence in the obtained results. The technical report CENELEC/TR 50646 which defines the specifications for reversible DC substations, states the currently unaddressed standardization needs for the effective characterization of reversible DC substations. In particular, the report lists a series of key performance indexes that should be proved by the reversible DC substation provider and that are currently not standardized: i) energy saving, ii) performance in terms of harmonic compensation on AC and DC side, iii) performance in terms of reactive power compensation, and iv) determination of efficiency at different levels of the converter group and for different operation modes (traction, regeneration). Further to this, triggered by INRIM in 2021, the CENELEC Subcommittee SC TC9XC launched a consultation among national committees regarding the update of CENELEC/TR 50646 or a new work item proposal. Currently, the assessment of power transformer losses connected to an electric converter takes place in the factory under nearly ideal, grid conditions. However, there's an urgent need to comprehend losses in real-world grid scenarios with harmonics and varying loads. The situation with AC/DC and DC/DC converters is analogous, with loss determination relying on simulations and lab verification, falling short in representing actual operating conditions in transportation systems. Crucially, there is a need for information on the impact of AC/DC converter harmonics on the efficiency of the supplying power transformer (CENELEC TC14).

3 Scientific Excellence

3.1 New calibration facilities for DC transducer

The calibration services for the electric power provided by national metrology institutes are nowadays focused on sinusoidal conditions and refer to DC or pure sinusoidal waveforms from 40 Hz to 100 kHz, for voltage and current amplitude of hundreds of volts and tens of amperes. Also, the determination of losses of power transformers by their manufacturers is presently performed at purely sinusoidal supply conditions. For DC substations, there is additional impact of harmonics generated by the AC/DC converter on the efficiency of the feeding power transformer. However, the extent of this impact is largely unknown, and power transformer acceptance tests do not take into account the extra (iron and copper) losses introduced by harmonics. The project will develop new traceability for DC dynamic signals (voltage and current ramps) with slew rates ranging from 500 A/s to 10 kA/s and from 100 V/s to 10 kV/s with amplitudes up to 1200 A and voltage 3 kV. The overall target uncertainty will be 0.01 %. This will be a major and challenging step to the state of the art given the present lack of dynamic calibration CMCs in the BIPM KCDB [5]. Moreover, the project will upgrade the systems developed in the 16ENG04 MyRailS project by providing traceable systems for AC and DC distorted power measurement even under dynamic conditions, up to 20 kV 300 A AC and 4 kV 3600 A DC. These systems will emulate the relevant load fluctuation experienced in the transportation systems.

3.2 Accurate on-site losses of the converter group

The project [1] will develop a new measurement infrastructure for the traceable on-site determination of losses/efficiency of energy conversion inside non-conventional DC substations for railway applications. The developed methodology will be unique in that: it will allow the first-ever determination, on-site, of the losses of HV-LV power transformers, AC/DC, DC/AC and DC/DC converters under real operating conditions. The infrastructure will allow to perform the loss determination with an overall uncertainty less than 10 % of the losses, even under distorted signal conditions. Moreover, the input-output methodology will be able to provide reliable determination even for losses value lower than 3 % of the rated power. With these results, new insights will be achieved in the loss mechanisms of transformers and converters under non-ideal situations. Since the measurement system will be also able to monitor the harmonic content introduced by the reversible substation on both AC and DC sides up to 20 kHz, losses can be correlated to grid and converter conditions, including active power terms brought along by harmonics, so that the impact of harmonics on the transformer and converter losses can be quantified for the first time.

3.3 Energy saving performance of transportation systems with non-conventional DC substations

Technical specifications of new traction supply systems or new rolling stock, nowadays, include requirements on energy efficiency. Receptivity is one of the new energy-efficiency-oriented requirements that, however, has no standard definition, and most of all no standardised method of determining it. The project will develop a novel hybrid methodology based on a combination of distributed measurements performed both on-board and at substations and a power flow model that allows the quantification under real operating conditions of the energy saving provided by the non-conventional substations. Uncertainty can be evaluated if a combined technique of modelling and measurement is applied, testing the system in a range of representative conditions. Such model-assisted system energy efficiency validation has never been proposed to the best of our knowledge. The quantification of the uncertainty associated of the power/energy measurements, a deep analysis of the influence quantities (traffic conditions, DC line and AC grid configuration), the correct weighting of the various operating conditions and the extrapolation to untested operating conditions are able to quantify the reliability and uncertainty of statements on energy saving. The approach will thus address the priority required by the IEC/CENELEC railway committees, including TC9X.

4 Conclusion

The International Union of Railway (UIC) estimated that the investment in a bidirectional substation is approximately 655,000 Euros, which, according to the studies analysed, can be amortised in approximately five years. It has been estimated that the traction energy savings, which depend on the network's operational specificities, can be up to 40 %. The project will promote the implementation of these energy-efficient technologies by providing means and standardised methods for assessment of the energy efficiency of the railway system. The project will impact industries operating in the field of design and installation of up-to-date supply systems for rails, railway infrastructure managers and train operating companies. The development of reliable methodologies to estimate the energy-efficiency improvement of the railway infrastructure can support further incentive policies in the framework of the European Green Deal.

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